

Supporting information

MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ nanorods synthesized using NiO nanoparticles for hydrogen evolution in anion exchange membrane water electrolysis

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In Figure S1 equivalent electrical circuit used for evaluation of the impedance spectra measured using 78.5 cm² electrolysis cell is shown. Used equivalent electrical circuit is literature based and it was used in agreement with previous experience accumulated during studying anion exchange membrane water electrolysis cells.^{1,2} Element L represents inductance, which is mostly present due to the cables connecting the potentiostat and studied cell. Inductance is typically visible at high frequencies of the perturbing signal.

Value R_s stands for ohmic resistance of the measured system, including resistance of the connecting cables, current feeders, electrodes and electrode compartments separator. In the well constructed cell, the main contributor to this quantity represents the electrode compartments separator. The R_s value corresponds to the $Z''=0$ at high frequencies of the perturbing signal.

Values R_{p1} and R_{p2} correspond to polarisation resistances, which are related to the charge transfer through the electrolyte|electrode boundary. R_{p1} and R_{p2} are thus directly related to the kinetic of the anode and cathode reaction respectively. In the case of one electrode reaction (anodic oxygen or cathodic hydrogen evolution respectively) is significantly slower than the second one, the equivalent electrical circuit can be simplified neglecting the values R_{p2} and $CPE2$ representing the faster reaction. This is the case of NiCo₂O₄ used on anode side. $CPE1$ and $CPE2$ are constant-phase elements. CPE represents capacitor with distributed value of capacity. It is typically used to characterise the 3D electrodes. Value of CPE thus describes the capacity of the electric double layer of the electrolyte|electrode boundary.

Value R_{por} describes resistivity of the electrolyte filling pores of the 3D electrode. Correspondingly, value $C1$ is also connected with capacity of the electric double layer on the 3D electrode pore walls.

Figure S1: The equivalent circuit used for evaluation of EIS measured using 78.5 cm² cell. L [H] (inductance of connecting cables), R_s [Ω] (system resistivity), R_{p1} and R_{p2} [Ω] (polarisation resistance), $CPE1&2$ [$F s^{n-1}$, where n represents frequency dispersion with the range of 0 to 1] (constant phase element), R_{por} [Ω] (resistance of liquid electrolyte in Ni foam pores), $C1$ [F] (capacity of the double layer on the pore walls of the Ni foam).

Figure S2: STEM images and elemental mapping of NiMoO₄ precursor b) Mo, c) Ni, d) O.

Figure S3: TEM micrograph (bright field) of MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ (600 °C).

Figure S4: TEM bright field of $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ a) 500 °C and b) 600 °C.

Table S1: Elemental NiMoO_4 composition obtained by XPS

	Mo	Ni	O
Element Percentage	9.3%	9.6%	81.2%
Experimental stoichiometry ^a	1	0.7	4.4

^a Experimental stoichiometry normalised to Mo.

	Mo/Ni	Ni/Mo	Mo/O	Ni/O	Mo+Ni/O
Experimental elements ratio	0.97	1.03	0.11	0.12	0.23

Table S2: Elemental $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (500 °C) composition obtained by XPS

	Mo	Ni	O
Element Percentage	10.1%	2.4%	88.74%
Experimental stoichiometry ^a	1	0.2	4.3

^a Experimental stoichiometry normalised to Mo

	Mo/Ni	Ni/Mo	Mo/O	Ni/O	Mo+Ni/O
Experimental elements ratio	4.15	0.24	0.12	0.03	0.14

Table S3: Elemental $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (600 °C) composition obtained by XPS

	Mo	Ni	O
Element Percentage	10.9%	5.0%	84.1%
Experimental stoichiometry ^a	1	0.3	3.8

^a Experimental stoichiometry normalised to Mo

	Mo/Ni	Ni/Mo	Mo/O	Ni/O	Mo+Ni/O
Experimental elements ratio	2.20	0.45	0.13	0.06	0.19

Table S4: composition (%) relative to the different oxidation states of Mo by XPS.

	Mo (0) %	Mo (IV) %	Mo (V) %	Mo (VI) %
$\text{NiMoO}_4/\text{Ni}_{\text{foam}}$ (previous work)	2.6	28	8.3	61
NiMoO_4	-	-	4	-
$\text{MoO}_2/\text{Ni}_{\text{foam}}$ 500 °C (previous work)	22.2	57.9	16.5	3.4
$\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (500 °C)	0	7	35	58
$\text{MoO}_2/\text{Ni}_{\text{foam}}$ 600°C (previous work)	17.1	65.9	13.9	3.1
$\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (600 °C)	1	36	9	54

Figure S5: a) Comparison of bare NiO nanopowder [3] then MoNiO₄ precursor grown onto NiO and MoNiO₄/Ni foam from previous work [4]. b) Comparison spectra of MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ 500 °C and MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ 600 °C.

Figure S6: Comparison between MoO₂/Ni_{foam} 600 °C (previous work) and MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ (600 °C). LSV registered at 1 mV s⁻¹ @ 1600 rpm, 0.1 M KOH.

Figure S7: Nyquist plot for a) $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ ($500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and b) $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ ($600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), recorded at different potentials.

Figure S8: fit results for $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ ($600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) at -0.1 V vs RHE .

Element	Freedom	Value	Error	Error %
R1	Fixed(X)	37	N/A	N/A
R2	Fixed(X)	4,9	N/A	N/A
CPE1-T	Fixed(X)	0,0002551	N/A	N/A
CPE1-P	Fixed(X)	0,8	N/A	N/A
R3	Free(+)	134,5	2,4759	1,8408
CPE2-T	Free(+)	0,0019835	8,9794E-05	4,527
CPE2-P	Free(+)	0,84953	0,01467	1,7268

Figure S9: Equivalent circuit for $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (600 °C) at -0.1 V vs RHE with relative circuital elements values.

Figure S10: Nyquist plots of the EIS measurements using the $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C cathode and anodes with IrO_2 or NiCo_2O_4 catalysts respectively. EIS measured in the frequency range 100 kHz–10Hz, with maximal amplitude 10 mV at cell voltage 1.6 V

Figure S11: Comparison between MoO₂/Ni_{foam} 600 °C (previous work) and MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ (600 °C). Cell test performed with Ni foam anode at 60 °C, 1 M KOH feed to the anode.

Table S5: comparison of different electrocatalysts for HER at -10 mA cm⁻².

Electrocatalyst	Overpotential (mV)	Electrolyte	Ref.
Ni-MoO ₂ /NF	38.3	KOH 1 M	5
Ti@Ni(OH) ₂ -NiMoS	180	KOH 1 M	6
Ni/MoO _{2-x} @NF	27	KOH 1 M	7
MoNi/NiMoO _x	9	KOH 1 M	8
NiMoN	20	KOH 1 M	9
NiMo@ZnO/NF	110	KOH 1 M	10
QAMN	240	KOH 0.1 M	11
MoO _{3-x} NiMoO ₄ 600 °C	190	KOH 0.1 M	This work

Table S6: Performance comparison of literature AEMWE data with Ni-Mo cathodes

Anion Exchange Membrane	Anion Exchange Ionomer	Cathode Catalyst	Anode catalyst	Electrolyte	Cell temp. °C	A cm ⁻² @ Vcell	Durability data	Ref.
FAA-3-PK-130	Fumasep FAA-3-film	MoO ₃ -xNiMoO ₄ (600 °C)	Ni foam	1 M KOH @ anode	60	0.82 @2	50 h 1 A cm ⁻²	this work
FAA-3-PK-130	--	MoO ₂ /Ni	Fe-MoNi/Ni	1 M KOH @anode	60	0.55 @2	300 h 0.5 A cm ⁻²	previous work [4]
FAA-3-PK-130	Fumasep FAA-3-film	MoO ₃ xNiMoO ₄ (600 °C)	IrO ₂	1 M KOH	50	0.9@1.8		this work
FAA-3-PK-130	Fumasep FAA-3-film	MoO ₃ xNiMoO ₄ (600 °C)	NiCoO ₄	1 M KOH	50	1.0@2.0		this work
PTFE-Sustainion	Nafion	Ni-Mo	Fe-Ni-Mo	1 M KOH @cathode	80	1.0 @1.57	--	[12]
FAA-3-50	FAA3	NiMo/K ^B	NiFe (85:15 at.%)	1 M KOH @anode	50	1.0 @1.8	2000 h 1 A cm ⁻²	[13]
PVBC-MPy/35%P EK-cardo	--	Ni-Mo	Ni-Fe	1 M KOH	60	0.5 @2	42 h 0.5 A cm ⁻²	[14]
FAA-3-PK-130	--	MoNi/NiMoO _x	Co ₂ (OH) ₃ Cl/FeOOH	1 M KOH	25	0.5 @ 3.05	1600 h 0.2 A cm ⁻²	[8]
Sustainion® X37-50	--	NiMo/TP-4	NiFe/TP-4	1 M KOH	50	--	100 h 1 A cm ⁻²	[15]
PFTP-13	--	20 mg cm ⁻² Ni-Fe	20 mg cm ⁻² Ni-Fe	1 M KOH cathode	80	1.6 @2.0	1000 h, 0.5 A cm ⁻² , 60 C, no degr	[16]

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